

Accelerating Digital Transformation in TVET: Challenges and Insights for TVET Staff Training

Khalil Bahloul¹, Ibrahima Diallo¹, Therrezinha Fernandes¹

¹UNESCO-IIEP, Dakar, Senegal
k.bahloul@iiep.unesco.org
i.diallo@iiep.unesco.org
td.kinkin@iiep.unesco.org

Abstract. This study investigates the digital transformation of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) across Africa, a specific focus on the issue of digital training for TVET staff. It aims to provide an overview of the current state, identify best practices, and propose actionable recommendations for accelerating digital adoption. Employing a case study methodology, the research examines five key nations—Rwanda, Chad, Nigeria, Madagascar, and Tunisia—representing Africa’s diverse regional economic communities, selected based on their existing technical plans, political will, and infrastructure capacity. The study highlights a significant gap in digital literacy among TVET educators. While countries recognize the importance of digital skills, implementation remains challenging. Madagascar’s the National Training Institute for Public and Private TVET Personnel (INFor) demonstrates a proactive approach through digitized library resources and Open-Distance E-Learning (ODEL) training, yet faces limitations in scope.

The findings show that integration of digital tools relies heavily on educator training rather than more equipment provision. Implementation of digital tools is hindered by resource constraints and a lack of comprehensive, structured programmes. Recommendations emphasize the need for integrated training plans, strategic digital transformation frameworks, and sustained political and financial commitment.

Keywords: TVET, Educator training, Digitalization, African context.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated digital adoption, pushing African governments, technical partners, and private sectors to rethink their strategies for delivering education and skills training. However, the shift to digital learning has also revealed a gap: the success of TVET digitalization not only relies on equipment and infrastructure but particularly on the digital competencies of educators and managers.

to support the Pan-African Initiative for the Digital Transition of TVET and Skills Development Systems—a large-scale international effort across Africa—the [X] conducted a study between 2020 and 2022 to evaluate the progress of digitalization within technical and vocational education and training (TVET). The study aims to invite reflection on the strengths and weaknesses of the development of technology in technical and vocational education and training (TVET). It addresses several aspects of the TVET system and led to the development of five country reports as well as a global synthesis report covering these aspects, namely, the development of digital infrastructure and environment, the digitalization of curricula, the development and strengthening of trainers and supervisory staff's capacities as well as financing for the digital development of TVET.

This article is based on the results of the previously cited study and focuses on one aspect addressed in the study and explores the key issues surrounding digital training for TVET staff, drawing insights from case studies conducted in Rwanda, Chad, Nigeria, Madagascar, and Tunisia. It highlights both the challenges and some lessons learned shaping the digital future of TVET in Africa.

2 Methodology

This study's methodology outlined clear criteria for selecting five countries, one from each of the five regional economic communities (RECs) in Africa, to conduct case studies. The selection of countries was based on the following criteria: relatively favorable contexts for digital development, presence of technical plans, political commitment (TVET strategy, TVET policy, etc.), engagement with infrastructure development (direct or indirect), capacity to drive the digital transformation of TVET.

Table 1. Africa's five RECs, along with their internet penetration rates and selected countries, are as follows:

Community of states	Population [1]	Internet penetration [2]	Selected country
East African Community (EAC)	173 million people	32% internet penetration	Rwanda
Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS)	200 million people	12% internet penetration	Chad
Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)	390 million people	41% internet penetration	Nigeria
Southern African Development Community (SADC)	345 million people	51% internet penetration	Madagascar
Arab Maghreb Union (AMU)	101 million people	50% internet penetration	Tunisia.

The study employed structured questionnaires to gather data, using an inverted funnel survey approach [3] starting with general questions and gradually moving to more specific ones. These questions, as well as discussions with the interlocutors focused on key aspects, including: structure of the education and TVET system, existing of vocational

skills policies, laws, and initiatives, existing of projects and coordination in terms of information and communication technology (ICT) and or digital transformation in the TVET sector, digital transformation efforts and their implementation levels, curriculum development and quality assurance mechanisms, TVET partnerships, major challenges and needs for adjustment.

A total of 376 individuals occupying diverse roles — including strategic officials from ministries, directors of training institutions, trainers, learners, as well as representatives of partner companies and professional organizations — were surveyed through questionnaires across the five countries studied. The distribution of respondents by country is presented in figure 1 below. This methodology survey approach [4] aimed to establish comprehensive understanding of the digitalization landscape in TVET across the selected regions, facilitating evidence-based recommendations and best practices in digital training for TVET staff.

Fig. 1. : People surveyed by country

3 Results

3.1 Key issues in digital training for TVET staff

Madagascar. In application of the terms defined in the Educational Sectoral Plan, and by the need to properly frame the training requests of administrative agents and TVET teachers, the Malagasy Ministry of Technical Education and Vocational Training (METFP) created the National Training Institute for Public and Private TVET Personnel (INFor), an organization attached to and dedicated to this specific training for both the public and private sectors. This institute was created in 2001 to respond to training demand from the TVET regional directorates and public and private TVET establishments [5]. INFor has also taken the initiative to digitize the books of the Library of the

Lycée Technique du Génie Civil, thanks to the implementation of an application dedicated to the database management of books, for on-screen reading of the scanned books, classified in catalogues and non-downloadable digital bookshops.

Distance training of TVET teachers and trainers is an immediate concern for INFor. A training course on the use of ODEL (Open-Distance E-Learning) software has been organized thanks to a collaboration with the African Development Bank [6]. Thus, in 2021 teachers of technical high schools and school officers have benefited from training on the creation of a digital teaching module and the use of the Moodle LMS installed at the information system department of the METFP. The objective of this training was to ensure continuity of training despite barrier measures caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Nigeria. In Nigeria, there is no available systematic training programme for TVET teachers and instructors. Any staff member willing to do capacity building has to organize it at their own expense; similarly, TVET trainers, and anyone else in charge of such training, build their own programme without it necessarily being based on an effective needs analysis and without following a rigorous progression plan. In the case of our study, over 52 per cent of tertiary TVET respondents said that their instructors lacked the necessary ICT skills. A 2021 report on the assessment of technical teachers and instructors in 276 technical colleges indicates that a total of 56.58 per cent of technical teachers and instructors have low to very low ICT skills [7]. In the Open, Distance, Flexible, and Online Learning (ODFEL) policy and strategy document developed in 2019, the council highlighted the major challenge in its implementation as “the lack of qualified professionals to support the implementation of ODFEL” [8].

The Nigerian government estimates that by 2030, 95 per cent of teachers and instructors should be digitally literate. To achieve this, training needs to be integrated into initial and in-service training plans. However, the National Policy and Strategy for a Digital Economy does not specify how the training will be operationalized [9]. The National Education Policy (NPE) from 2004 stated that ‘teacher education should continue to be emphasized in educational planning and development’ in recognition of the “central role of quality teachers in the provision of quality education at all levels” [10]. Regarding the need for support in developing and implementing a digital transformation strategy in TVET institutions in Nigeria, 69.6% of TVET headteachers acknowledged requiring assistance in drafting the strategy for their institutions. Furthermore, 91% of headteachers expressed the need for support in implementing the strategy (Figure 2 and 3).

Fig. 2. : Need help in drafting digital transformation strategy

Fig. 3. Need help in implementing digital transformation strategy

Given that 91% of TVET headteachers expressed the need for support in implementing digital tools and practices, there is a clear need to move beyond a deficit-based model of professional development. Instead, a transformative approach should be adopted—one that positions TVET educators as proactive agents of change. This involves empowering staff to design and deliver technology-enhanced lessons, develop digital learning content, and integrate immersive tools such as virtual and augmented reality into their teaching. Nigeria’s engagement with UNESCO’s **Campus Africa** flagship programme exemplifies this shift, as the country begins embedding digital skills into TVET curricula to foster innovation and responsiveness in its workforce development strategy.

Rwanda. In Rwanda, the joint programme by the ICDL and Microsoft Foundations revealed that between 2019 and 2020, 50 per cent of TVET trainers received ICT training through the Rwanda Trainers' Training Institute (RTTI), supported by the

programme. TVET managers have not received any training beyond what they may have acquired at university. TVET directors still lack digital skills. [11].

Rwanda has the ambition to become an ICT Hub of the region, the government aims to transform the country from an importer to exporter of ICT skilled manpower. Indeed, Rwanda has developed since 2016 a National Digital Talent Policy which aimed to increase Digital Skills and Literacy across all levels of Rwandan society both in terms of quality and quantity [12].

Building on these foundational efforts, Rwanda's commitment to developing a national strategy for digitizing its Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) system—supported by UNESCO and other partners—marks a promising step forward. This strategy seeks to address existing capacity gaps by integrating digital technologies into teaching and learning, thereby enhancing the quality and relevance of TVET. The findings of this study, particularly the Rwanda country report, offer a strong basis for this strategic effort, which is framed by the Quadruple Helix Innovation Model [13]. This model promotes co-creation of digital policy through inclusive partnerships among government, industry, academia, and civil society.

Tunisia. In Tunisia, the National Centre for Training of Trainers and Training Engineering (CENAFFIF) is responsible for developing training plans for building capacity of human resources in the sector, both for trainers and managers. The International Center for Trainer Training and Pedagogical Innovation is the second actor in the field of continuing education, at the level of the Ministry of Education.

Of the Tunisian heads of vocational training establishments surveyed, 97% recognized the critical importance of digital technical training. However, 83 per cent of them emphasized the need to complement it with additional training in areas such as change management, project management, risk management, stress management, team building, governance, educational and training structure management, and quality management.

Table 2. Development of digital skills of management staff

Statement	Disagree	Partially Agree	Strongly Agree
Training is a key component of the digital transformation project	0%	3%	97%
You consider the training you receive sufficient to manage the daily operations of your institution	13%	30%	57%
You consider the training you receive sufficient to manage the digital transformation of your institution	83%	14%	3%

The quality of the training you have received so far is satisfactory	10%	77%	13%
--	-----	-----	-----

A community of practice, comprising several thousand teachers integrating ICT into their professional activities, has been active since the early 2000s. Training sessions have been organized across all education delegations, and national and regional summer schools have been held to train trainers, expanding the network of teachers using ICT and accelerating innovation. However, the Ministry of Education's decision to halt this process in 2008 significantly affected the ICT integration initiative and negatively impacted the broader education system. In early 2010, a certification programme — the Certificate of Competence in Computer Science, was introduced [14]. Other courses have been developed, such as the Microsoft Imagine Academy, which offers a certification course based on the UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers [15]. The Microsoft Imagine Academy was launched in 2015 in 30 vocational training centers spread across various governorates of the Republic and generalized in 2018 for teachers and trainees through the Ministry of Higher Education. The National Centre for Technology in Education has also set up, in 2020, a distance learning platform called 'The Virtual School' and intended for all stakeholders in the education system: students, parents, and teachers, with several digital educational services organized in dedicated spaces according to cycles, levels, and disciplines.

3.2 Lessons learned and priority needs

Despite efforts, teacher, trainer, and supervisor training in digital skills remains limited in the countries of the study. Even when promising initiatives are introduced, they often face the same challenges as broader teacher training programs: a lack of prioritization. As a result, these initiatives are vulnerable to funding cuts and shifts in political priorities.

Despite notable improvements in the ICT sector, this study highlights several ICT-related TVET gaps and priority needs. First, contradictory TVET statistics point to the importance of strengthening management information systems for better steering. In addition, there is a lack of a clear framework and strategy for collaboration between ICT policy makers, the private sector, and TVET providers. The respondents of the study acknowledge shortcomings in digital training for teachers, instructors, executives, and managers; the need for renewed technological equipment; and the necessity of an ongoing, well-structured digital policy within TVET. There is also a demand for a clear, applicable qualifications framework for different levels of TVET digitalization, alongside an emphasis on digitalizing the curriculum across technical, technological, and scientific pathways. The creation of inter-country networks for training programmes, technological tools, and evaluation instruments would facilitate effective resource sharing and dissemination. Furthermore, flexible and scalable pathways between

different TVET structures must be established to meet evolving digital skills requirements. Developing ICT training modules that cater to the specific needs of each field—linked with virtual learning and practice communities—is also imperative. Finally, implementing guidance systems based on computerized labour market information would help learners choose suitable careers and promote stronger inclusion of girls and women in TVET programmes.

3.3 Recommendations

To support a transition from bottlenecks and unmet needs toward a future of innovative digital transformation in TVET, these key recommendations can be synthesized under a strategic vision for inclusive, agile, and future-oriented TVET systems, anchored in digital innovation and ecosystem-wide collaboration.

Institutionalize Digital Training through Structured and Inclusive Frameworks: Countries like Nigeria and Madagascar reveal the absence or fragility of institutional structures for systematic digital training. A strong recommendation is to develop and institutionalize national frameworks that integrate digital training into both pre-service and in-service TVET teacher education and ensure these frameworks are embedded within existing national education policies.

Shift from Deficit-Based Models to Empowerment-Based Pedagogy: move away from viewing TVET educators as passive recipients and instead empower them as digital innovators, especially by promoting active pedagogical models where staff co-create and deliver digital content.

Establish multi-stakeholder governance structures, using models such as the Quadruple Helix Innovation Model, to foster public-private-academic-civil society partnerships for co-creation of digital policies and strategies.

Promote and finance national and regional teacher networks, peer-learning platforms, and digital champions who can cascade skills and innovations. Experiences from Tunisia show the effectiveness of communities of practice in sustaining ICT integration.

Align Digital TVET with Labour Market Intelligence by integrating computerized labour market information systems (LMIS) to guide curriculum design and learner orientation.

4 Conclusion

A country's entire digital development depends more on its training capacities and the digital skills of its educators than on the provision of abundant equipment. Each country seems to have become aware of the challenges of the trainers' capacities development without being able to meet them, as the task is complex and concerns all levels of the system.

This study illustrates the needs of addressing the digitalization of TVET in the sampled countries. The Pan-African Initiative for the Digital Transition of TVET and Skills

Development Systems in Africa provides an excellent opportunity for building sustainable digital ecosystems in Africa, based on the findings of this multi-country study.

References

1. Kemp S.: Essential insights into how people around the world use internet, mobile devices, social media and e-commerce, we are Social Hootsuite Digital 19 p.33 (2019)
2. African Union: 2019 African regional integration report, Voices of the RECs (2019)
3. Taherdoost, H.: Designing a Questionnaire for a Research Paper: A Comprehensive Guide to Design and Develop an Effective Questionnaire. *Asian Journal of Managerial Science*, 2022, vol 11, 8–16 (2022)
4. Malhotra, N. K.: Questionnaire design and scale development. *The handbook of marketing research: Uses, misuses, and future advances*, 83–94 (2006)
5. Madagascar education ministry: Ministerial Decree No. 2001-029 Amending Decree No. 92-431 of April 2, 1992, establishing and organizing the Resource Center for Personnel of Technical and Vocational Education Institutions (CeRes) (2001)
6. IIEP-UNESCO: Management of Trainers and Supervisory Staff in TVET: Case study of four African countries: Benin, Ethiopia, Madagascar and Senegal, 47–55 (2022)
7. KOMTEK Engineering Services, World Bank IDEAS Project. Baseline study of technical teachers and instructors in Nigeria to assess the availability, working conditions and the situation around training and further training, (2021)
8. NBTE. National TVET Policy and Strategy on Open, Distance, Flexible and E-Learning, (2019)
9. Federal Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy, Nigeria National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy 2020–2030, (2019)
10. Federal Ministry of Education, Nigeria National Policy on Education (2004)
11. NISR Rwanda Annual Statistical Yearbook, National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda. Chapter V Education, 29–47, (2021)
12. Rwanda Ministry of Youth and ICT, 201. National Digital Talent Policy (2016)
13. Dagogo W. L-J and Ndebele C.: Fostering Digital Inclusion in TVET Teacher Training: Insights from Quadruple Helix Innovation Model. *E-Journal of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences*, 2022, vol 3, 648-664 (2022)
14. CNTE Tunisia: Training curriculum of the National training center of education technology of Tunisia, (2015)
15. UNESCO: UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers version 3, 2018, 27–41 (2018)